

MtrunA17_Chr7g0273141, MthGSHSb, putative homoglutathione synthase

NcORF11: MtrunA17_Chr7g0273141_2F_2-136_135

Species: *Phaseolus vulgaris*

Taxonomic group: eudicots, legumes

Annotation: homoglutathione synthetase (hgshs)

Protein ID: AAF98157.1

Nucleotide seq. ID: AF258320.1

Conservation:

amino acid level: 91%

nucleotide level: 89%

dN/dS: 0.111, p-value: 0.037

Consensus

Mt

Pv

MtrunA17_Chr7g0273141, MthGSHSb, putative homoglutathione synthase

NcORF11: MtrunA17_Chr7g0273141_2F_2-136_135

```
1 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 75 80 90 100 110
CATCATATTTACAAACCATACGGAAAAACATTTGGCAGAAAATTAATCAAGAAGGAGAAAATTCCTGCCAGATGGAACACTTTCTGTGTATGGATGGACAAGCAGTTCGCAATCGTTTACT
H H I T T I R K T L A E I N Q E G E I L P D G T L S V Y G W T S S R N R L L
120 130 135
TCCGAGCTGGCTATACACCAGT
P S W L Y T S
```

Species: *Populus trichocarpa*

Taxonomic group: eudicots, non-legumes

Annotation: glutathione synthetase, chloroplastic

Protein ID: XP_024456199.1

Nucleotide seq. ID: XM_024600431.2

Conservation:

amino acid level: 91%

nucleotide level: 83%

dN/dS: 0.045, p-value: 0.019

Consensus

Mt

Pt

MtrunA17_Chr7g0273141, MthGSHSb, putative homoglutathione synthase

NcORF12: MtrunA17_Chr7g0273141_1F_625-816_192

Species: *Cicer arietinum*

Taxonomic group: eudicots, legumes

Annotation: glutathione synthetase, chloroplastic-like isoform X1

Protein ID: XP_027188838.1

Nucleotide seq. ID: XM_027333037.2

Conservation:

amino acid level: 98%

nucleotide level: 93%

dN/dS: 0.051, p-value: 0.009

Consensus

Mt

Ca

MtrunA17_Chr4g0009054, MtPHO2-A, ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2

NcORF51: MtrunA17_Chr4g0009054_1F_1300-1440_141

Species: *Vicia villosa*

Taxonomic group: eudicots, legumes

Annotation: probable ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2

Protein ID: XP_058771571.1

Nucleotide seq. ID: XM_058915588.1

Conservation:

amino acid level: 95%

nucleotide level: 90%

dN/dS: 0.025, p-value: 0.006

MtrunA17_Chr4g0009054, MtPHO2-A, ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2

NcORF53: MtrunA17_Chr4g0009054_1F_3370-3927_558

Species: *Cicer arietinum*

Taxonomic group: eudicots, legumes

Annotation: probable ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2

Protein ID: XP_004485781.1

Nucleotide seq. ID: XM_004485724.4

Conservation:

amino acid level: 96%

nucleotide level: 92%

dN/dS: 0.060, p-value: 1.110E-06

(continued on the next slide)

MtrunA17_Chr4g0009054, MtPHO2-A, ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2

NcORF53: MtrunA17_Chr4g0009054_1F_3370-3927_558

Species: *Morus notabilis*

Taxonomic group: eudicots, non-legumes

Annotation: probable ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2

Protein ID: XP_010108186.1

Nucleotide seq. ID: XM_010109884.2

Conservation:

amino acid level: 88%

nucleotide level: 77%

dN/dS: 0.029, p-value: 0.094

(continued on the next slide)

MtrunA17_Chr4g0009054, MtPHO2-A, ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2

NcORF53: MtrunA17_Chr4g0009054_1F_3370-3927_558

Species: *Rhynchospora pubera*

Taxonomic group: monocots

Annotation: ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme family protein

Protein ID: KAJ4731383.1

Nucleotide seq. ID: JAMFTS010007231.1

Conservation:

amino acid level: 82%

nucleotide level: 72%

dN/dS: n/c, p-value: n/c

(continued on the next slide)

MtrunA17_Chr4g0009054, MtPHO2-A, ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2

NcORF53: MtrunA17_Chr4g0009054_1F_3370-3927_558

Consensus

Mt

Rp

Consensus

Mt

Rp

Consensus

Mt

Rp

Consensus

Mt

Rp

MtrunA17_Chr4g0009054, MtPHO2-A, ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2

NcORF54: MtrunA17_Chr4g0009054_2F_4052-4372_321

Species: *Glycine max*

Taxonomic group: eudicots, legumes

Annotation: probable ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2

Protein ID: XP_014621290.1

Nucleotide seq. ID: XM_014765804.3

Conservation:

amino acid level: 96%

nucleotide level: 92%

dN/dS: 0.061, p-value: 0.024

Consensus

Mt

Gm

MtrunA17_Chr4g0009054, MtPHO2-A, ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2

NcORF54: MtrunA17_Chr4g0009054_2F_4052-4372_321

Species: *Alnus glutinosa*

Taxonomic group: eudicots, non-legumes

Annotation: probable ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2

Protein ID: XP_062161121.1

Nucleotide seq. ID: XM_062305137.1

Conservation:

amino acid level: 83%

nucleotide level: 75%

dN/dS: 0.057, p-value: 0.175

Consensus

Mt

Ag

MtrunA17_Chr4g0035414, MtbZIP60b, S class bZIP transcription factor

NcORF60: MtrunA17_Chr4g0035414_3F_168-335_168

Species: *Mucuna pruriens*

Taxonomic group: eudicots, legumes

Annotation: bZIP transcription factor

Protein ID: RDY01331.1

Nucleotide seq. ID: QJKJ01002791.1

Conservation:

amino acid level: 98%

nucleotide level: 91%

dN/dS: 0.036, p-value: 0.010

Consensus

Mt

Mp

MtrunA17_Chr4g0052121, MtKAS II, ketoacyl-ACP synthase II

NcORF65: MtrunA17_Chr4g0052121_1F_982-1161_180

Species: *Physcomitrium patens*

Taxonomic group: bryophytes

Annotation: 3-oxoacyl-[acyl-carrier-protein] synthase II, chloroplastic

Protein ID: XP_024391557.1

Nucleotide seq. ID: XM_024535789.2

Conservation:

amino acid level: 95%

nucleotide level: 73%

dN/dS: n/c, p-value: n/c

Consensus

Mt

Pt

Data S13. Visual demonstration of conservation at the amino acid level for eight selected ncORFs. The dataset shows evidence for purifying selection (dN/dS ratios and their statistical significance computed in MEGA-X v10.2.6). Details of the calculations can be found in Data S14. Corresponding alignments in MEGA format can be extracted from Data S15). Color of asterisks shown above the alignments: black – a synonymous mutation; blue – a non-synonymous mutation that preserves properties of an amino acid in the chain (corresponds to a plus-sign in NCBI-BLASTN alignments); red – a non-synonymous mutation that does not preserve properties of an amino acid in the chain (corresponds to an empty space in NCBI-BLASTN alignments). Graphical data were generated in Geneious® R7.1.9. P-values are from Z-test for significance of dN/dS deviation from one. Only p-values without Bonferroni adjustment are shown. P-values after the adjustment are above 0.05, except for Slide 7. Even very strong conservation signatures obvious in some of the alignments in this dataset may not signify translation of a ncORF if it originates from a very recent frameshift that had no immediate effect on fitness (see Discussion).

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